

Deposition of:

Tonya Henderson

LVNV FUNDING

v.

ERIC WISEMAN

Case No. 24CV000841

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COURT OF COMMON PLEAS
FRANKLIN COUNTY, OHIO

_____)
LVNV FUNDING, LLC,)
)
Plaintiff,)
)
vs.)
)
ERIC WISEMAN,)
)
Defendant.)
_____)

Case No.
24CV000841

30(B)(5)
Deposition of: TONYA HENDERSON
(via videoconference)
Pursuant to: Notice
Date and Time: Thursday, October 17, 2024
10:38 a.m.
Place: Greenville, South Carolina
Reporter: Tracy L. Allen, RPR, RMR
(via videoconference)
Notary Public - State of Ohio

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1	I N D E X	
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3	TONYA HENDERSON	PAGE
4	EXAMINATION BY MR. BARNES	4
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6	- - -	
7	(No exhibits.)	
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1 But as to the date that Resurgent or
2 someone for Resurgent printed it and gave it to
3 whichever attorney requested it first, LVNV
4 Funding is not aware of that date.

5 Q. Okay. And then that CVS -- CSV
6 file. So that's a comma-separated value file,
7 right?

8 A. If that's how you refer to it. I
9 know it as a text file.

10 Q. So that text file -- you actually
11 reviewed the text file, correct?

12 A. That is correct, yes, sir.

13 Q. Okay. And so in the text file --
14 which we don't have because you haven't
15 produced it. So under open date, how does that
16 text file appear? Is it in columns?

17 So, again, I'm not a computer guy,
18 so how does that text file present information?
19 Is it just a bunch of -- explain that text file
20 to me, please, if you will.

21 MR. GENTRY: Objection. Multiple
22 questions.

23 MR. BARNES: Okay.

24 BY MR. BARNES:

25 Q. Did you understand my question,

1 Ms. Henderson?

2 A. Not really. Do you want me to --

3 MR. GENTRY: You ended with explain

4 to me. That's not a question at all.

5 Please ask a question.

6 MR. BARNES: Thanks, Boyd.

7 BY MR. BARNES:

8 Q. And then so explain how that text
9 file is presented.

10 MR. GENTRY: Objection. Again, it's
11 not a question.

12 MR. BARNES: It is.

13 BY MR. BARNES:

14 Q. Go ahead, Ms. Henderson.

15 MR. GENTRY: Ask a question, she'll
16 answer it.

17 MR. BARNES: Boyd, I appreciate your
18 input.

19 BY MR. BARNES:

20 Q. But, Ms. Henderson, if you could
21 answer that question.

22 A. The text file shows the information
23 and it is separated by commas.

24 Q. Okay. So is it in lines or is it
25 just this big, massive document?

1 A. You and I might have different
2 explanations or descriptions of a big, massive
3 document. But just like any text file, it is
4 text that -- it's a little harder for humans to
5 view, works great for computer systems. But it
6 is a text file that shows the information for
7 each account. And the fields are separated by
8 commas.

9 Q. Great. So let's take a look at
10 LVNV54. So LVNV54, under the heading column
11 C_balance_fees, it has a number identified as
12 5.82645E-13.

13 Do you see that?

14 A. Yes, sir.

15 Q. Okay. So in the CVS file -- or CSV,
16 not CVS, CSV, that number, 5.862 -- or 826454
17 is represented in that text file?

18 A. Yes.

19 Q. With the E-13?

20 A. I believe so.

21 Q. Okay. What does that mean?

22 A. LVNV does not know. Marlette --
23 this is information that -- the entire file is
24 information that Marlette prepared to show data
25 for each of the accounts sold.

1 this file. Our understanding is that this is
2 the information that comes from their systems.

3 They could have one system of record
4 or a different payment system, multiple
5 systems, and they upload this.

6 So, truly, Marlette knows for each
7 field, as far as the formatting, it is
8 completely Marlette, because they created this.
9 And the data, as you see the data, has not been
10 changed or altered.

11 BY MR. BARNES:

12 Q. But we don't have a way to verify
13 that unless seeing the underlying CSV file.

14 A. I am --

15 MR. GENTRY: Wait a minute.

16 Objection. That's not a question,
17 Ms. Henderson. That's just a statement.

18 BY MR. BARNES:

19 Q. Is there a way to verify that that's
20 the actual data without the CSV file?

21 A. Well, this is the CSV file. It's
22 the printed view of Mr. Wiseman's data on that
23 CSV file.

24 And as an authorized representative
25 for LVNV Funding, and under oath today, I did

1 review the electronic transmission and have
2 compared every piece of data that is contained
3 in that file.

4 And as I said previously, pages
5 LVNV50 through 64 are completely 100 percent
6 true and accurate.

7 The easiest thing we could do if we
8 wanted to lie was to make it look nice and
9 pretty, but we do not.

10 It is exactly how each seller
11 prepares their file and they send it to us.
12 And we do not alter their data or change their
13 data even if formatting would make it look a
14 whole lot better.

15 BY MR. BARNES:

16 Q. And we, you're saying LVNV, or are
17 you saying we as in Resurgent?

18 A. I'm saying Resurgent is the holding
19 entity for this file, but LVNV Funding is aware
20 that there's no changes ever made and that the
21 data file is created by the seller at that
22 time.

23 As an authorized representative of
24 LVNV Funding, I have verified it all again and
25 it is 100 percent accurate.